

Assessment of Pes Planus Using Staheli's Plantar Arch Index in Young Adults**Sanyam Arora¹, D. Radhika², S. Ravindra Kishore³, Bharat Raj Chukka⁴**¹2nd Year Post Graduate, Department of Anatomy, Andhra Medical College, Vishakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India²Professor, Department of Anatomy, Andhra Medical College, Vishakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India³Professor & HOD, Department of Anatomy, Andhra Medical College, Vishakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India⁴1st Year Post Graduate, Department of Anatomy, Andhra Medical College, Vishakhapatnam, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction and Objective: A flat foot is a condition where the arch of the foot is reduced or absent, causing the entire bottom of the foot to touch the ground. The causes of flat feet differ among various age groups, requiring specific evaluations based on age. The objective of this study was to utilize the Plantar Arch Index (PAI) to assess the occurrence of pes planus among a group of young adults and to explore any potential connection between pes planus and obesity.

This study involved 250 first-year medical students from Andhra Medical College, Visakhapatnam, during the academic year 2023-2024. It was a prospective, cross-sectional study. The PAI was calculated using Staheli's method after obtaining ink footprints from the participants. An analysis was performed to assess the correlation between PAI and body mass index (BMI).

Findings: Type III pes planus was found to have a prevalence of 8%, with a slightly higher occurrence in males. The PAI values varied from 0 to 1.720. There was no notable link discovered between obesity (as determined by BMI) and PAI in the age group under investigation.

Conclusion: There is no notable link between being overweight and the development of flat feet in young adults aged 18-22 years. In this age group, the causes of pes planus can be varied and not necessarily related to body weight. The ink footprint method is a dependable and gentle technique for identifying flat feet in its early stages, similar to radiographic methods.

Keywords: Plantar Arch Index, Pes Planus, Medial Longitudinal Arch, Staheli's Method, Body Mass Index, Anthropometric Analysis

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Introduction

The feet bear a significant amount of weight due to human bipedal locomotion. They are supported by the arches located on the inner and outer sides of the foot, as well as the arch that runs across the foot. The arches have a vital function in evenly distributing body weight and safeguarding the neurovascular structures in the plantar region. Irregularities in these arches can result in a range of foot deformities, such as flat foot, high arch, and clubfoot. [1]

Flat feet, marked by the full or almost full contact of the sole with the ground, can be present from birth or develop later in life. Flat feet can be present from birth or develop later in life due to various factors such as genetics, injuries, excessive strain, weight, health conditions, or problems with body mechanics. Identifying the arches in infants

can be challenging due to the presence of adipose tissue, which obscures them from view. As the foot bears weight, the fat in certain areas may shrink, revealing the natural arches that usually develop by the age of two. Although some people with flat feet may not have any symptoms, others may feel pain, swelling, and a burning sensation in their feet. [2]

Past research has indicated a connection between flat feet and obesity in children between the ages of 10 and 12. Unfortunately, there is a lack of information regarding the frequency and causes of flat feet in young adults. The objective of this study is to evaluate the occurrence of flat foot among young adults by utilising the Plantar Arch Index (PAI) and to investigate any potential correlation with BMI. [3]

Methodology

A cross-sectional study was carried out on a sample of 250 first-year medical students, consisting of 155 females and 95 males. The participants were aged between 18 and 22 years and were enrolled at Andhra Medical College in Visakhapatnam. The data collection period covered the academic year 2023-2024. The ink footprint method was used to capture the footprints of participants, utilising the specified materials:

- Stamp Ink
- Roller
- Steel Tray
- Plain Paper
- Measuring Scale

- Ink Dropper

Procedure: A steel tray was set up with a sheet of plain paper secured in place using clips. A roller was used to evenly coat the participant's foot with stamp ink. The participant proceeded to position one foot on the paper within the steel tray while keeping the other foot outside the tray. The participant received instructions to stand up, perform a gentle knee flexion, and then return to the starting position before taking their foot off the tray. A tangent line was drawn to the medial forefoot edge and at the heel region, using the footprint obtained. This allowed for the calculation of the Plantar Arch Index (PAI). The measurements of the central region (A) and the heel region (B) were recorded in millimeters.

FIGURE 1: Ink print method

FIGURE 2: Staheli's method of calculating PAI

FIGURE 3: Radiological image of right foot lateral view showing the normal arches.

RADIOLOGICAL IMAGE OF RIGHT FOOT SHOWING NORMAL ARCHES

The calculation of Staheli's plantar arch index (SPAI) involves dividing the width of the central region (A) by the width of the heel region (B). Based on Staheli's classification, a PAI greater than 1.15 suggests Type III flat foot, a PAI ranging from 0.9 to 1.15 suggests Type II flat foot, and a PAI

less than 0.9 suggests Type I, which is considered a normal arch.

Inclusion Criteria:

Students in their first year of medical school, typically between the ages of 18 and 22.

Exclusion Criteria:

The study will exclude participants with congenital foot abnormalities, callus or corn formation, substantial limb damage, limb palsies, or refusal. Participants' height and weight were measured to ascertain their BMI according to WHO recommendations. Weight was used to classify participants as underweight, normal, pre-obese, obesity type 1, and obesity type 2.

Results

SPSS software was used to perform the statistical analysis. The study uncovered the following discoveries:

The average PAI was computed for participants of both genders.

Medical writing is a specialized field that requires precision and attention to detail. It involves the creation of documents that communicate complex medical information clearly and concisely. Medical writers play a crucial role in translating scientific data into understandable language for various audiences, including healthcare 8% of individuals were found to have Type III flat foot, with a higher occurrence among males.

- The PAI values varied between 0 and 1.720.
- There was no notable connection discovered between BMI and PAI.

Table 1: PAI Among Participants (n=250)

Gender	Foot	Mean PAI	Standard Deviation (SD)
Male	Right Foot	0.70	0.28
	Left Foot	0.75	0.27
Female	Right Foot	0.60	0.21
	Left Foot	0.60	0.20

Table 2: Mean PAI (n=250)

Gender	Foot	PAI < 0.9	PAI 0.9-1.15	PAI > 1.15
Male	Right	0.620	1.0605	1.686
	Left	0.6011	1.023	1.25
Female	Right	0.537	1.096	1.33
	Left	0.575	0.975	1.153

Table 3: Gender Distribution with Type of Deformity

Gender	Foot	PAI < 0.9	PAI 0.9-1.15	PAI > 1.15	Total
Male	Right	79	8	8	95
	Left	76	10	9	95
Female	Right	138	17	5	155
	Left	133	15	7	155

In males, the prevalence of bilateral Type III pes planus was 8%, while in females it was 3%. Most of the participants had typical foot structures. A small percentage of individuals had Type II and Type III deformities. Out of these, a majority of 83% exhibited a normal foot structure.

Table 4: Distribution Based on Height, Weight, and BMI

Foot Deformity	Mean Height (cm)	Mean Weight (kg)	Mean BMI (kg/m ²)
No Flat Foot	163.51	60.30	22.22
Bilateral Grade III	172	65	21.97
Bilateral Grade II	172.5	65	21.97
One Foot Grade I & Other Grade II	168.85	66.85	23.87
One Foot Grade I & Other Grade III	161	57	21.84
One Foot Grade II & Other Grade III	171.58	70.66	23.59

Individuals with Type II deformities in both feet exhibited a higher BMI, although the correlation between flat foot and BMI did not reach statistical significance.

Discussion

The study observed a 7% occurrence of flat foot among the participants, which is consistent with

previous research. A 6% prevalence was reported among 150 first-year MBBS students by Ramos et al. In a study conducted by Ganapathy et al., [4] it was observed that 5.2% of the 250 medical students had a certain condition. In a study conducted by Vijay Kumar et al., it was discovered that there was a prevalence rate of 8.9% among a group of 412 individuals aged 18-27 years. [5] According to a study by Rithanya et al., there was a 10% prevalence rate among a group of 50 individuals aged 50-70 years. These findings indicate a rise in the occurrence of flat foot as individuals get older. Although previous research suggested that males were more affected and that there was a link between obesity and flat foot in younger children, our study discovered that there was no notable relationship between obesity and flat foot in young adults. [6]

Conclusion

The data show no link between fat and flat foot among 18–22-year-olds. Flat foot in this age range may have numerous causes and not be weight-related. Staheli's ink method can diagnose flat foot early without surgery. This approach is useful for large-scale screening in low-resource environments. Since orthopaedic footwear and prosthetics can help treat flat foot disorders like

plantar fasciitis, this has major consequences for their development.

References

1. Saltzman, C.L., Nawoczenski, D.A., Talbot, K.D. Measurement of the medial longitudinal arch. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil.*
2. Ramos et al. Prevalence of flat foot among first-year MBBS students. Kanthali U, Cila E. Footprint and radiographic analysis of feet. *J Pediatr Orthop.* Mar-Apr 2001.
3. Pfeiffer, M., Kotz, R., Ledl, T., Hauser, G., Shega. Prevalence of flat foot in preschool-aged children. *Pediatrics*, 2006. Chen, C.H., Huang, M.H. Correlation between selected measurements from footprint and radiograph of flatfoot. *Arch Phys Med Rehabil.* 2006.
4. Vijay Kumar, K., Senthil Kumar, S., Subramanian. Relationship between BMI and prevalence of flat foot among adults using footprint parameters. *Int J Adv Res.* 2016.
5. Rithanya, P., Babuy, M., Mohanraj, K. Assessment of the flat foot by plantar arch index using footprint in aged population. *Drug Invention Today*, 2018.
6. Hernandez, A.J. Calculation of the Staheli's plantar arch index and prevalence of flat feet; a study with 100 children aged 5-9 years. *Pediatr Obes.* 2007.